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The effect of dynamic operating conditions on the thermoacoustic response of hydrogen rich flames in an annular combustor

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ABSTRACT

Self-excited thermoacoustic instabilities in symmetric annular combustion chambers typically give rise to spinning, standing and mixed azimuthal modes which are time-varying in nature and occur in a highly noisy environment due to turbulent combustion. We investigate the effect of linear ramps of increasing and decreasing equivalence ratio on the operating limits and thermoacoustic dynamics, from near lean blow-off to near flashback, in a laboratory scale annular combustor. The combustor features 12 lean-premixed hydrogen–methane flames at a fuel composition of 70% hydrogen and 30% methane by power. Equivalence ratio ramps were conducted for different thermal powers $P=4, 6$ and 8 kW per burner and three different ramp times $t_{ramp}=5, 20, 60$ s to simulate dynamic operation. It was found that ramping leads to self-excited instabilities that exhibit repeatable modal dynamics which depend on thermal power, ramp direction and duration. Different types of hysteresis were observed between the upward and downward ramps which affected the amplitudes and the stable operating range. The hysteresis phenomena also showed repeatable behaviour in terms of the nature and orientation angle. In one specific case, the simultaneous existence of two spinning modes was observed before the appearance of mode hopping leading to both an increase in frequency and doubling of the amplitude. High-speed OH* chemiluminescence of the flames showed that the mode hopping was accompanied by a change in the flame shape which becomes more compact and distributed.

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1. Introduction

The motivation for this study stems from the recent drive by the gas turbine industry towards hydrogen combustion and dynamic operation to provide zero carbon power generation [1,2]. When operated flexibly, hydrogen fired gas turbines can play a vital role in accelerating the energy transition by providing stability to the grid through dynamic operation (varying load) enabling increased penetration of intermittent renewable power sources.

One of the main factors limiting the operating range of gas turbines are self-excited thermoacoustic oscillations [3–5]. These instabilities result from a constructive coupling between acoustics, flow, and the fluctuating heat release rate in the combustor. In annular combustion chambers, this is typically manifested by the propagation of acoustic waves in both azimuthal directions as observed in aeroengines and industrial combustors [5–7], and repro-

duced in laboratory combustors [8–10] as well as in high fidelity numerical simulations [11].

Over the last decade, the nature of azimuthal modes has received significant attention from the scientific community. The self-excited modes are generally classified as either standing modes whose nodal line remains fixed or slowly rotates around the annular chamber, spinning modes whose nodal line spins at the speed of sound, or a combination of both, forming mixed modes. A repeatable feature of azimuthally symmetric geometries with turbulent flames are time-varying changes in the azimuthal mode types resulting in instantaneous changes between spinning, standing and mixed modes at a fixed operating point [7–11]. These types of effects, which we will refer to herein as modal dynamics for simplicity, have not yet been observed in the case of laminar flames [12].

The effects of explicit symmetry breaking on azimuthal modes has also been investigated in a number of studies considering the effects of bulk swirl [8,13,14], different burner geometry [14–19] and baffles [20]. By contrast, the effects of explicit symmetry breaking on the nodal line and the orientation angle, has

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not been investigated in detail except for [20]. In a symmetric annular combustor, the geometry is periodic, so counter propagating azimuthal waves with the same wavelength have no prescribed phase relationship. Therefore any observed preferred orientation of the nodal line indicates that small asymmetries are present which may be due to non-uniform geometry or flow conditions [16,18,21].

Although the occurrence of self-excited instabilities under transient operating conditions is very relevant for full-scale engines, for example during take off for aeroengines or under variable loads for power generation, it has only recently started to receive more attention. Earlier studies have shown that the presence of inherent noise from turbulence or external noise imposed by an actuator influences the thermoacoustic dynamics in the vicinity of subcritical Hopf bifurcations [22]. It has also been shown that hysteresis could be exploited to control operating limits [23]. More recently, in an afterburner configuration, an earlier onset of instability was reported for an increasing rate of change of the air flow rate [24]. Bonciolini and Noiray [25] showed that sufficiently fast ramps in equivalence ratio could bypass instability islands in a model gas turbine combustor. In a separate study by the same authors it was shown that thermal effects can also affect the system response under transient load [26]. In a multi-nozzle arrangement, both the absolute difference and the duration of the transient fuel staging affected the amplitude growth and decay of the instabilities [27].

The above mentioned studies only consider single flame configurations with the exception of the multi-nozzle array of [27], but none have been reported in symmetric annular combustors with turbulent flames which exhibit more complex modal response. Prieur et al. [28] showed that hysteresis altered the stability maps in the laminar flame matrix burner configuration of the MICCA facility at EM2C. By increasing and decreasing equivalence ratio at constant air flow, stability maps showed a “dual mode” region which depended on initial conditions. However, the paper did not consider the effects of turbulent flames or controlled linear ramps in equivalence ratio on the operating limits to simulate dynamic operation.

In this paper we characterise the system response during controlled linear ramps of increasing and decreasing equivalence ratio which features repeatable modal dynamics and hysteresis phenomena in an annular combustor with turbulent bluff body stabilised flames. The effect of different operating conditions and ramp parameters on amplitude, modal dynamics and hysteresis is investigated.

The paper is organised as follows: first we introduce the experimental setup, the operating and ramping conditions as well as the procedure to determine the nature of the azimuthal mode. Then the focus is put on the general system response to the ramping of the operating conditions before the hysteresis phenomenon is investigated in terms of the amplitude of the instabilities. Subsequently the effect of the ramping of the operating parameters on the nature of the mode and on the anti-nodal line positions is investigated before a mode hopping phenomenon is described.

2. Experimental setup, operating conditions and ramping procedure

Experiments were conducted using the atmospheric annular combustion chamber described in previous papers [8,9] with some modifications including the use of burners without swirl [29] as well as water cooled inner and outer enclosures. The setup of the annular combustor and a drawing displaying the dimensions are shown in Fig. A.1.

A premixed fuel-air mixture is fed into a cylindrical plenum that conditions and divides the flow into 12 axisymmetric burners. The burners are comprised of 150 mm long tubes with bluff bodies of 13 mm diameter equally spaced around the circumference

Table 1

Operating conditions in terms of the thermal power per injector P , the hydrogen power fraction P_H , the hydrogen volume fraction V_H , the adiabatic flame temperature of the mixture T_{ad} , the laminar flame speed of the mixture s_L , the bulk velocity \bar{u} , ramp direction and time, outer wall temperature when the ramps are initiated $T_{o,wall}$ and settling temperature of the cooling for the inner and outer wall $T_{i,c}/T_{o,c}$. The temperatures correspond to settling temperatures for ramps with increasing Φ .

P [kW]	4	6	8
P_H		0.7	
V_H		0.876	
Φ	0.4–0.625	0.4–0.7	0.4–0.65
T_{ad} [K]	1376–1825	1376–1954	1376–1869
s_L [m s ⁻¹]	0.076–0.513	0.076–0.706	0.076–0.575
\bar{u} [m s ⁻¹]	18–12	27–17	36–24
Ramp direction	Increasing and decreasing		
Ramp time [s]	5, 20, 60		
$T_{o,wall,70}$ [°C]	420	435	455
$T_{i,c}$ [°C]	22	27	30
$T_{o,c}$ [°C]	21	23	25

of the annular combustor (30° between each injector). The outer diameter of the injector is 18.95 mm. The inner and outer walls of the chamber were 120 mm and 300 mm long respectively, with diameters of 127 mm and 212 mm. Water cooled walls were introduced to achieve long run times and achieve approximately constant wall temperatures. A separate cooling circuit for the inner and outer walls was employed. For the outer wall, chilled water flowed through four circumferentially spaced inlets near the combustor back plane which exited four outlets at the top. A similar arrangement was used for the inner wall but with 3 inlets and outlets. A schematic is shown in Fig. A.1b and c.

A summary of the operating conditions is reported in Table 1. The combustor is fueled with a perfectly premixed mixture. The fuel is composed of 87.6% hydrogen and 12.4% methane by volume. This translates to approx. 70% and 30% in terms of the power respectively (calculation based on the lower heating values given in ISO/TR 15916:2015). Each of the 12 individual burners was operated with a fixed power P of 4, 6 or 8 kW. Controlled linear ramps in terms of the equivalence ratio Φ covered the range of 0.4 to 0.625 (4 kW), 0.4 to 0.7 (6 kW) and 0.4 to 0.65 (8 kW) with the leanest conditions being near the lean blow-off limit and the richest near flashback.

The procedure for the controlled ramps was as follows: the burner was ignited near the lean blow-off limit for upward ramps and near the flashback limit for the downward ramps and remained at a fixed set point until the outer wall temperature $T_{o,c}$ reached thermal equilibrium. The air flow was then linearly increased or decreased with a ramp time t_{ramp} of 5, 20 or 60 s. After each ramp the combustor was cooled down, reignited and preheated before the next ramp was initiated. Wall temperatures were measured with up to 13 thermocouples (RS PRO Type K 1.5 mm). The cooling water flow was kept constant with an inlet water temperature of $T_{in} = 10$ –13 °C. Depending on the operating point (P and Φ), the settling temperatures at the outlet varied slightly.

Typical temperature histories are shown in Fig. A.2(a) and (b) for one position located on the outer wall, 70 mm above the combustor back plane. The time period between the red lines denotes the ramping interval. Ramping cycles for increasing Φ were started 60 s after ignition, as shown in Fig. A.2(a). Ramping cycles for decreasing Φ were started 30 s after ignition to avoid long operation of the combustor close to the flashback limit.

The temperatures listed in Table 1 correspond to the temperatures that were reached when the increasing equivalence ratio ramps are initiated. It is important to appreciate that the temper-

Fig. A.1. (a) Experimental setup of the model annular gas turbine combustor with 12 bluff body stabilised flames, (b) technical drawing, (c) detailed view displaying the in- and outlets of the cooling walls and (d) top view highlighting the azimuthal position of the microphones.

Fig. A.2. Outer wall temperature $T_{o,w}$ at $x_{T3} = 70$ mm and $\Phi = 30^\circ$, cooling water temperature of the inner wall $T_{i,c}$ and of the outer wall $T_{o,c}$ for an (a) increasing and (b) decreasing equivalence ratio ramp with $P = 8$ kW and $t_{ramp} = 5$ s. (c) Longitudinal (at $\Theta = 30^\circ$) and (d) circumferential (at $x = 70$ mm) wall temperature distribution at $t = 60$ s. Circular markers describe the outer wall, triangular markers the inner wall. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

atures change as a result of the ramping procedure and do not remain constant.

Figure A.2 (c) and (d) shows the longitudinal (at $\Theta = 30^\circ$) and circumferential (at $x = 70$ mm) temperature profiles. The wall temperatures are clearly dependent on the power and decrease in downstream direction. Small differences between the wall temperature of the inner and outer wall were observed. In circumferential direction one notices that the temperatures differ for positions next to a burner or between two burners. The mean temperature variation in the azimuthal direction is approximately 10–20 °C and symmetric on a sector by sector basis which reasonably suggests that heat transfer does not have a significant impact on symmetry breaking.

To characterise the acoustic modes, 8 Kulite (XCS-093-05D) pressure transducers were mounted at three azimuthal ($\Theta = 0, 120, 240^\circ$) and up to four longitudinal positions (see Fig. A.1). The signals were recorded with a sampling frequency of 51.2 kHz and digitised using a 24-bit DAQ system (NI model 9174).

Fluctuations in the heat release rate, $\dot{Q}(t)$, were obtained using a high-speed camera (Phantom V2012) with intensifier and UV filter ($\lambda = 310$ nm, FWHM 10 nm). The camera captures the OH*-chemiluminescence of the full annulus from the top (via a cooled mirror) or from the side. If images are acquired from the side, a shortened outer wall segment was placed on top of a quartz glass segment, thereby resembling the length of the cooled outer walls.

There was a small delay time between a decreased/increased mass flow through the mass flow controllers (MFC) and the actual mixture composition in the burner. Considering the wide range of flow velocities, this delay time was not constant but was estimated to be below 0.3 s for all cases.

3. Mode determination

To analyse the modes, we use the quaternion ansatz proposed in [30] that fully describes the acoustic pressure field associated azimuthal eigenmodes in annular combustion chambers. It

Fig. A.3. (a) Bloch sphere representation of the state of an azimuthal eigenmode, (b–d) illustrate the 3 types of states: pure spinning, pure standing and mix of the latter two states.

provides a set of four variables (Amplitude A , nature angle χ , orientation angle θ and temporal phase φ) which vary slowly with respect to the acoustic time-scale and constitutes a well-defined description of the state of the azimuthal thermoacoustic eigenmode. Using this notation, the acoustic pressure field corresponding to the first azimuthal mode (which is the subject of the experiments in this work) can be represented as

$$p(\Theta, t) = A \cos(\Theta - \theta) \cos(\chi) \cos(\omega t + \varphi) + A \sin(\Theta - \theta) \sin(\chi) \sin(\omega t + \varphi). \quad (1)$$

where θ is the slowly varying real-valued angular position anti-nodal line between $-\pi$ and π . It is important to note that at any instant, a state whose orientation angle is θ is the same as the state defined by $\theta + \pi$ and θ is therefore plotted between 0 and π . The slowly varying real-valued angle $\chi(t)$ indicates whether the azimuthal eigenmode is a standing wave ($\chi = 0$), a pure clockwise (CW) or counterclockwise (CCW) spinning wave ($\chi = \mp\pi/4$) or a mix of both for $0 < |\chi| < \pi/4$. The nature angle is directly related to the more commonly used spin ratio s by $s = \tan(\chi)$. Finally, the variable φ is the temporal phase which is related to slow and small changes of the instantaneous frequency. Even though φ is needed to fully describe the pressure field based on the quaternions, we will concentrate on A , χ and θ in this work. The reason for this is that φ does qualitatively not provide additional insight into the nature of the instability. For constant operating conditions φ shows a flat PDF without a preferential value and $\dot{\varphi}$ is centered around 0, indicating very little drift relative to the instability frequency. During the equivalence ratio ramp itself the frequency changes. This leads to constant rotation of φ which nonetheless exhibits a flat PDF but $\dot{\varphi}$ is not centered around zero any more.

While a comprehensive description of the quaternion formalism is available in [30], we provide details of how we handle and post-process the pressure signals in Appendix A.

A useful representation of the state of the thermoacoustic mode in terms of the first three slow-flow variables A , θ and 2χ at a given instant t is illustrated by Bloch sphere shown in Fig. A.3. The amplitude corresponds to the sphere radius A , the nature angle 2χ defines the latitude and the anti-nodal line direction θ is the longitude. Thermo-acoustic states positioned at the poles correspond to spinning modes, standing modes are located along the equatorial plane and mixed modes are located at intermediate longitudes between the equator and the poles.

4. Overview of the system response

Figure A.4 plots representative spectrograms for typical $t_{ramp} = 20$ s ramps and 3 different powers with the dominant self-excited modes shown on the left hand side. The self-excited modes were characterised using dynamic pressure measurements from 8 locations shown in Fig. A.1 and the corresponding dominant modes calculated from an acoustic solver [31] using an approximated temperature field divided into a burnt region in the combustor volume and unburnt region everywhere else. While the solver identifies multiple modes in the relevant frequency range, the number of modes can be reduced by comparing with reconstructed modes from the pressure measurements using the multiple microphone method which showed that the observed mode was of first azimuthal order (see Suppl. material for more information). The predicted frequencies, longitudinal and azimuthal components were in good agreement. Similar to earlier studies of combustion instabilities in annular combustion chambers open to atmosphere (e.g. [32]), the amplitude of the mode is relatively low in the combustion chamber as instability is driven by the acoustics of the injection unit. Note that in contrast to earlier investigations [8,29], the frequency was comparably lower due to a combination of factors including different fuels and operation at very lean equivalence ratios resulting in lower temperatures.

For $P = 4$ kW the instability frequency slowly increases during the ramp. The combustor becomes unstable after around 70 s initially having a frequency of 881 Hz which increases to 900 Hz at the final operating condition and corresponds to the mode 1A1L, with first azimuthal and first longitudinal orders. For $P = 6$ kW, initially a low-amplitude 1A2L mode with a frequency between 1100 and 1150 Hz is unstable and switches to the high-amplitude 1A3L mode which has a frequency around 1330–1370 Hz. Note that both modes coexist for a short time; the features of this mode hopping process are presented later. Only the 1A3L mode ($f = 1370$ Hz) is self-sustained when the power is increased to $P = 8$ kW. The predicted frequencies of the passive acoustic simulation (solution of the Helmholtz equation with non-uniform temperature field without active flame element) were 836 Hz, 1124 Hz and 1327 Hz respectively.

Figure A.5 plots the effect of upward and downward ramps on the time-series of p' , A , χ and θ when the burners are operated at 4 kW. Upward and downward ramps are shown on the left and right hand sides of the figure respectively. During the upward ramp the transition from a stable state to a limit cycle is accompanied by a linear increase in A beginning at approximately $t > 105$ s.

The evolution of χ , shows that the self-excited mode initially transitions from a low-amplitude standing mode to a switching spinning mode whose spinning direction switches periodically, to a mixed clock-wise (CW) mode and back to the quasi-periodic switching of the spinning direction. The angular position of the anti-nodal line also follows a clear trend remaining constant during intervals where χ is not switching. However, when the modes are regularly switching their spinning direction, the anti-nodal line switches between $\theta = 60^\circ$ which is coincident with a burner and $\theta = 135^\circ$ which is in between two burners. The switching of θ occurs simultaneously with maxima and minima of χ , as shown in the detailed views provided on the right hand side of Fig. A.5 and in the joint PDFs in Fig. A.6.

The periodic evolution of χ manifest itself with a beating phenomenon in the acoustic signals of the individual microphones with amplitude oscillations of around 200 Pa. Figure A.6 shows that the modal dynamics follow a very clear pattern with one switching cycle (from 1 to 5 in Fig. A.6) taking around 0.75 s. The slight asymmetry in the joint PDFs also shows that the amplitude is larger when the mode spins in CW direction and that a CCW spinning direction is preferred. Preference for different spinning

Fig. A.4. From left to right: typical spectrograms at $P = 4$ kW, $P = 6$ kW and $P = 8$ kW. All spectrograms correspond to ramps with $t_{ramp} = 20$ s. Color denotes the amplitude and the red lines show the start and end of the equivalence ratio ramps. The left side of each subplot shows the result of a passive acoustic simulation depicting the corresponding mode shapes: 1A1L, 1A2L and 1A3L. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. A.5. Comparison of an increasing (a)–(d) and decreasing (e)–(h) equivalence ratio ramp with $t_{ramp} = 60$ s at $P = 4$ kW. The plot highlights the ramp from an equivalence ratio of 0.5 to the 0.625. (a) and (e) show the raw pressure signals corresponding to the upper microphones at 0, 120 and 240° ($p_{0,1} - p_{2,1}$). The dashed red line indicates the equivalence ratio. (b) and (f) indicate the amplitude, (c) and (g) the nature angle and (d) and (h) the orientation angle of the azimuthal mode. (i) to (l) correspond to detailed views at instants indicated by the shaded green area.

Fig. A.6. Joint PDF of amplitude, nature angle and orientation angle for the high-amplitude switching mode at $P = 4$ kW and $\Phi = 0.65$.

directions was previously observed in a similar set-up by Mazur [29] which was attributed to small imperfections in the azimuthal symmetry.

The system dynamics during the downward ramp is distinctly different. As Φ is linearly decreased, A remains approximately con-

stant while the spinning-direction-switching dynamics persist several seconds before starting to decrease. Instead of a linear decrease in A , a power law decay to stable conditions is observed. A further difference is that the system does not return to the low-amplitude standing modes observed near the bifurcation point during the upward ramp. Neither does it return to the mixed CW mode with a constant nature and orientation angle.

A likely reason for the different system response to the ramping direction are the different initial conditions. Ramping up from stable conditions the flames responds linearly to finite perturbations which excite standing modes near the bifurcation point. As A increases to limit-cycle conditions, the system favours spinning modes, in particular a state where spinning modes switch direction. On the downward ramps the initial conditions begin in the switching state under limit-cycles. Therefore, the flames do not respond linearly to changes in Φ resulting in hysteresis and changing the stable operating limits as discussed in the next section.

Fig. A.7. Comparison of an increasing (a)–(d) and decreasing (e)–(h) equivalence ratio ramp with $t_{\text{ramp}} = 20$ s at $P=6$ kW. The plot highlights the ramp from an equivalence ratio of 0.48 to the 0.7. (a) and (e) show the raw pressure signals corresponding to the four longitudinally spaced microphones at 0° ($p_{0,1} - p_{0,4}$). The dashed red line in (a) and (e) indicates the equivalence ratio. (b) and (f) indicate the amplitude, (c) and (g) the nature angle and (d) and (h) the orientation angle of the azimuthal mode. The solid lines show the mode at $f_3=1330\text{--}1370$ Hz, the dashed lines the mode at $f_2=1100\text{--}1150$ Hz.

Although the cooled walls minimise thermal inertia, as shown in Fig. A.2, they may still have a non-negligible effect on the system response.

Figure A.7 shows upward and downward ramps for $P=6$ kW. During the upward ramp, the 1A2L is first unstable, transitioning rapidly to the 1A3L mode resulting in a frequency jump from approximately $f_2 = 1150$ Hz to $f_3 = 1350$ Hz. The mode change occurs when Φ exceeds 0.6 (see the corresponding spectrogram in Fig. A.4). During the upward ramp, an 1A2L mode with a frequency f_2 becomes unstable, showing first a switching behavior before it becomes a predominantly CW spinning mode at ≈ 73 s until the ramp reaches $\Phi = 0.6$ when the 1A3L mode becomes unstable. These two modes of different longitudinal acoustic pressure distribution coexist, with no preferred θ . At $t=76$ s, these modes spin in opposite direction, then they become quasi-standing modes at around 78 s. After $t > 79$ s, the first mode disappears and the higher frequency mode dominates, resulting in a higher amplitude limit-cycle as an almost pure CW spinning mode.

A very similar evolution of the transient thermoacoustic dynamics is found during the downward ramp. The main difference is a reduced interval when both eigenmodes coexist. Interestingly, θ is significantly different for both ramp directions during the high-amplitude spinning mode which is expected to result from the different initial conditions. The combustor is ignited under stable conditions for the upwards ramp, which develops a clearly preferred orientation angle for the high amplitude spinning mode. For the downwards ramp tests, the combustor is ignited at a condition exhibiting a very robust, quasi perfectly spinning mode and then ramped down. During the first phase of the ramping down, the 1A3L mode remains quasi-perfectly spinning with a relatively fast drift of the preferred direction, at about 250 Hz, which is not that slow compared to the 1350 Hz of the acoustic time scale. The signature of this precession of the instantaneous state in the immediate vicinity of the pole of the Bloch sphere is hardly noticeable from the acoustic time traces. An interesting difference to Fig. A.5 is that the 1A2L mode shows a similar linear growth for both ramp directions.

Figure A.8 plots $t_{\text{ramp}} = 5$ s ramps for 8 kW and shows different behaviour. The combustor becomes thermoacoustically unstable, with a transient growth of the 1A3L mode from $\Phi=0.5$ and shows an irregular amplitude growth in contrast to the approximately linear growth observed for $P = 4$ and 6 kW. Initially, the limit cycle is a standing mode and the anti-nodal line has a clearly preferred position around $\theta = 60^\circ$. The standing mode undergoes a jump in amplitude at $t=63.7$ s which lasts 0.5 s until the mode suddenly becomes a CW spinning mode following a second amplitude jump. The standing wave component of the CW spinning mode shows a preferred anti-nodal line position at $\theta = 120^\circ$, which corresponds to a burner location.

On the downward ramp, a CW mode having a similar amplitude self-oscillates but the preferred anti-nodal line position is moved to a location between two burners at $\theta = 135^\circ$. When Φ is decreased the amplitude of this CW mode persists for a couple of seconds before decaying. The high amplitude standing mode observed in the upward ramp does not appear and the amplitude shows two main decay rates compared with the stepped amplitude profile of the upward ramp. The transition to a standing mode at an amplitude of 2000 Pa is accompanied with a switch to the same preferred anti nodal line position as during the increasing ramp.

5. Hysteresis of the thermoacoustic amplitude

The effect of different t_{ramp} and P on the operating limits is shown by the plots A versus Φ in Fig. A.9. The ramp times of 5, 20 and 60 s are colour coded with the thickness of the lines representing the standard deviation from a minimum of 7 runs for each case.

Figure A.9 (a) plots the effect of ramp times and direction for $P = 4$ kW. All upward and downward ramp sequences show hysteresis effects demonstrated by the shift in the bifurcation points for the different ramp time and directions. During upward ramps, the combustor becomes unstable at around $\Phi = 0.5$ for slow ramp times but remains stable until approximately $\Phi = 0.52$ for the fast ramp time. During the downward ramps there is a clear distinction

Fig. A.8. Comparison of an increasing (a)–(d) and decreasing (e)–(h) equivalence ratio ramp with $t_{ramp} = 5$ s at $P=8$ kW. The plot highlights the ramp from an equivalence ratio of 0.48 to the 0.7. (a) and (e) show the raw pressure signals corresponding to the upper microphones at 0, 120 and 240° ($p_{0,1} - p_{2,1}$). The dashed red line in (a) and (e) indicates the equivalence ratio. (b) and (f) indicate the amplitude, (c) and (g) the nature angle and (d) and (h) the orientation angle of the azimuthal mode.

Fig. A.9. Mean amplitude (line) and standard deviation (shaded) during the ramping procedure at (a) $P=4$ kW, (b) $P=8$ kW and (c) $P=6$ kW for three different ramp times (5 s ■, 20 s ■ and 60 s ■) and both directions. Arrowheads indicate the ramp direction. In (c) solid lines correspond the mode at $f_3=1330\text{--}1370$ Hz and the dashed (increasing Φ) and dotted (decreasing Φ) lines to the mode at $f_2=1100\text{--}1150$ Hz. Each data set corresponds to 7 ramps per ramp time and direction. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

in the hysteresis between the fast and slow ramp sequences. During the fast upward and downward ramps, A remains higher on the downward ramp relative to the upward ramp resulting in a small reduction in the stability range. This type of hysteresis, where the downward ramp reduces the operating limits relative to the upward ramp, has been observed previously in a number of single flame or Rijke tube experiments [3,25,33,34] and will be referred to as positive hysteresis, which can happen during transient varia-

tion of the bifurcation parameter, not only for subcritical Hopf bifurcations but also for supercritical ones as it was shown in [33].

Surprisingly, a different behavior is observed for the slower ramps which show that the downward ramps increase the stability limits relative to the upward ramps (negative hysteresis). During the slow upward ramps the system becomes unstable at around $\Phi = 0.5$ whilst slow downward ramps reach stable conditions between $\Phi = 0.55$ and 0.56. This type of hysteresis behaviour, where

the down ramp increases the stability limits compared to the upward ramp, differs from previously reported behaviour and to the best of the authors knowledge, this is the first time this type of hysteresis behaviour has been observed in flames.

Different behaviour is observed for the 8 kW cases as shown in Fig. A.9(b). Overall, they feature weaker hysteresis than the 4 kW cases but have instability amplitudes 4 times greater. Generally, two different hysteresis regions exist. One at lower A between $\Phi = 0.48$ and 0.52 and a second one at higher A between $\Phi = 0.56$ and 0.62 . Focusing on the longer 20 and 60 s ramp sequences first, positive hysteresis is observed for both ramp times in the higher Φ region. However the extents of these hysteresis regions differs with the 60 s ramps exhibiting a very weak hysteresis. Below approximately $\Phi = 0.6$, the slow downward ramps do not exhibit hysteresis as shown by the collapse in both ramping directions. However, below $\Phi = 0.52$ and when A drops below 1000 Pa, the 20 s ramp shows a second positive hysteresis. The fast ramp sequences exhibit different behaviour. A large positive hysteresis, is present on the downward ramp, occurring between $\Phi = 0.52$ and 0.62 . This corresponds to the observed plateau where the high amplitude standing mode occurs during the ramp up, which is not present during the ramp down.

Figure A.9 (c) plots the stability limits for the 6 kW ramping sequences where the frequency jump occurs from f_2 to f_3 due to the change in the mode from 1A2L to 1A3L denoted by the broken and solid lines respectively. A larger plot is used due to the extra complexity in the hysteresis behaviour due to the presence of the frequency/mode hop. The upward ramps show the 1A2L mode becomes unstable between $\Phi = 0.5$ and 0.52 and grows linearly for all three ramp speeds. The mode/frequency hop occurs between $\Phi = 0.62$ and 0.68 which shows both an increase in A of the 1A3L mode with a simultaneous decrease of A in the 1A2L mode. As soon as the amplitude of the 1A3L mode surpasses the amplitude of 1A2L, it rapidly increases to limit-cycle conditions. Strong positive hysteresis effects for the 1A3L mode are observed for all ramp speeds. The 1A3L mode maintains its high-amplitude limit-cycle over a larger range of operating conditions for decreasing ramp time. The complex interaction between the two modes shows that the decay in the 1A3L mode coincides with the reestablishment and growth of the 1A2L mode but the interval where both modes coexist is considerably shortened during the ramp down. The amplitude of the 1A2L mode then decays in a linear manner exhibiting considerably smaller hysteresis than the high amplitude 1A3L mode.

This type of hysteresis involving switch from one mode to another is typical of dynamic flame non-linearities induced by a flame response to acoustic perturbation that has a delay which depends on the oscillation amplitude. Such situation was investigated in [33] using a describing function analysis and is in line with the change of mean flame length that is observed in the present experiments as explained in the last section.

Overall, the longer ramp sequences of 20 s and 60 s show similar bifurcation points and hysteresis behaviour. The short ramp sequence 5 s shows a different bifurcation point and hysteresis behaviour. A potential explanation may be a time-scale effect related to thermal inertia of the combustor which is sensitive to the rate of change of temperature, such that at suitably fast ramp times the thermal inertial time-scale is much slower than the time scale of the equivalence ratio ramp. We note this is a conjecture and a larger range of ramp times are needed to further elucidate the dominant mechanisms at play.

6. Hysteresis of the nature and orientation angle

The hysteresis phenomenon is also manifested in θ and χ . First, the 4 kW cases are investigated in Fig. A.10. In terms of

χ , the slowest upward ramps transition from a standing mode to a switching spinning mode where χ oscillates between either spinning directions. From this periodically switching state, the mode evolves to stable spinning mode occurring for a short time around $\Phi = 0.55$ (see $t=119-123$ s in Fig. A.5) before returning to a switching spinning mode. During faster ramps up, the switching mode tends to be replaced by a CW mixed mode, and the transition to a switching mode always occurs but tends to be delayed to higher Φ . The hysteresis on the downward ramp shows a direct transition from the switching mode to stable bypassing the occurrence of the CW spinning mode. Except for the differences in the amplitudes, θ and χ follow the same path for all downward ramp times for decreasing Φ until stable conditions are reached.

The nodal line position shown on the right hand side of Fig. A.10 follows clear, repeatable trends for all of the seven runs, with small differences in the 5 s, which clearly indicates the presence of weak symmetry breaking in the system, due to small asymmetries in the geometry, the cooling system, the flow or the flame shapes for example.

In absence of switching modes, a very clear and reproducible path for both θ and χ is observed (see Fig. A.11) for all ramping sequences when the power is increased to 8 kW. The unstable modes show that on upward ramps standing modes become unstable as the amplitude grows and saturate to spinning modes. Figure A.11 also shows that the ramp time affects the saturation to spinning modes which occurs at lower Φ for decreasing upward ramp times. The opposite trend is observed for downward ramps. The orientation angle also closely follows the trends in χ .

While the 4 kW cases showed a clear tendency towards CW spinning modes, both spinning directions are observed for the 8 kW cases. The standing and the spinning mode do have the same preferred θ as the switching mode reported earlier: $\Theta = 60^\circ$ is positioned on a burner for the standing mode and $\Theta = 135^\circ$ positioned in between two burners for the spinning modes. Joint PDFs of θ and χ for the 6 kW cases are not presented here for brevity. Defined trends for θ and χ were observed when either of the two unstable modes were present. However, no discernible trends were observed during the coexistence of two modes.

7. Mode hopping

We now further investigate the mode hopping from the 1A2L to the 1A3L mode which occurs during the 6 kW ramps by investigating the flame dynamics. An additional measurement campaign was undertaken to obtain high-speed OH* chemiluminescence imaging at 10 kHz to provide side views of the flame as shown in Figs. A.12 and A.13. To provide optical access, a shorter version of the outer wall was placed on top of a short quartz segment. This will slightly change the thermal state but the modal behaviour and amplitude for the self-excited modes was found to be repeatable and closely matched the cooled-wall behaviour presented in previous sections. It is therefore reasonable to expect that the resulting flame dynamics are representative of the mode hopping.

The mean flame shapes for $\Phi = 0.65$ and 0.7 are shown in Fig. A.12 corresponding to a 1A2L CCW spinning and a 1A3L CW spinning mode respectively. As Φ is increased, it is accompanied by an increase in flame temperature as well as heat transfer to the bluff body which causes the mode to hop from the 1A2L mode to the 1A3L mode. This more than doubles the acoustic velocity amplitude, $u'/\langle U \rangle = 0.3$ to 0.65 evaluated from the multiple microphone method. This leads to a significant change in the mean flame shape and therefore the phase response of the flame. This is supported by the fact that the 1A3L mode is the only mode excited when the power is increased to 8kW (see Fig. A.4). The flame shape for the 1A2L mode is anchored at the edge of the bluff body with distinct flame brushes depicted by the elongated

Fig. A.10. Comparison of the joint PDFs of the nature and orientation angle for different ramping speeds and directions at $P=4$ kW. Each graph corresponds to 7 ramps. The first two columns represent the nature angle for increasing and decreasing equivalence ratio. The orientation angle is shown in the 3rd (increasing Φ) and 4th column (decreasing Φ). The ramp times are 60 s (1st row), 20 s (2nd row) and 5 s (3rd row). The region where the amplitude is below 100 Pa is masked.

Fig. A.11. Comparison of the joint PDFs of the nature and orientation angle for different ramping speeds and directions at $P=8$ kW. Each graph corresponds to 7 ramps. The first two columns represent the nature angle for increasing and decreasing equivalence ratio. The orientation angle is shown in the 3rd (increasing Φ) and 4th column (decreasing Φ). The ramp times are 60 s (1st row), 20 s (2nd row) and 5 s (3rd row). The region where the amplitude is below 100 Pa is masked.

Fig. A.12. Images of the mean flame shape at $P=6$ kW for $\Phi = 0.65$ (a) and $\Phi = 0.7$ (b) with the stream-wise distribution of heat release rate.

yellow to white regions. The mean flame shape of the 1A3L mode is distinctly different in two main ways: firstly, the flame is more compact and secondly, the heat release rate is more distributed as shown by the increase in OH^* intensity in the wake region (reduced gradient of OH^* across the flame). Comparing the stream-wise distribution of the integrated heat release rate (grey plots on the adjacent sides of the mean flame images) shows that the location of peak heat release rate has moved upstream. It is plausible to assume that this change in the flame shape will induce changes

to the FTF delay. The shorter time-lag leads to the higher frequency instability associated with the higher longitudinal mode. It is important to note that the 1A3L mode is approaching the flashback condition $\Phi = 0.72$.

The phase-averaged flame response over the limit cycles for each mode are plotted in Fig. A.13. The azimuthal spinning directions are indicated by the white arrows. Also, note that the flame is completely isolated from neighbouring flames (no flame-flame interaction) and oscillates strongly in axial direction for both

Fig. A.13. Phase averaged OH^* chemiluminescence from the side at $\Theta = 0$, at $P=6$ kW. The data was gathered during single runs at the specified Φ and the phase averages are based on 7000 images. $\dot{Q}_{norm} = 0.9\dot{Q}_{max}$.

operating conditions. In both cases, asymmetries in the flame response are shown relative to the direction of the azimuthal modes, which results in slight tilting to the right in the CCW direction for $\Phi = 0.65$ and to the left in the CW direction for $\Phi = 0.7$ as shown previously in [35]. For the 1A2L mode, this results in asymmetric shedding of the top part of the flame brush between $t/T = 3/8$ to $t/T = 5/8$ with increased \dot{Q} on the left hand side of the flame relative to the right hand side. The latter four panels also show a more pronounced flame roll-up on the left hand side relative to the right hand side.

Overall, similar dynamics of the 1A3L mode are observed but with some differences. Most notable is the flame roll-up process at $t/T = 4/8$ to $t/T = 5/8$ which occurs closer to the bluff body resulting from the reduced time-lag associated with the increased frequency of the longitudinal component. Since the flame is close to flashback conditions, it almost propagates back into the injector pipe as shown by the low value levels of \dot{Q} at $t/T = 3/8$. The asymmetric flame response of the flame due to the CW spinning mode is shown by slight tilting to the left hand side and the slight advancing of \dot{Q} on the right hand side. Due to the increased compactness and more distributed flame the peak values of \dot{Q} are closer to the bluff-body as found in the mean flame shape.

8. Conclusion

This work presents experimental observations during equivalence ratio ramps in an annular combustion chamber. Exhibiting self-sustained azimuthal combustion instabilities the system features phenomena that can only partially be explained by existing models in the literature or have not been reported before. The presented data condenses to several key observations:

- Both positive and negative hysteresis in terms of the amplitude during equivalence ratio ramps are observed. Thereby, the negative hysteresis phenomenon increased the stability range of the combustor, while the positive hysteresis decreased it. Generally, the hysteresis phenomena are heavily dependent on the ramping speed and direction, as well as the power the burner is operated at. In all cases, reducing the ramping time increased the amplitude difference between the upwards and the downwards ramps.
- A quasi-periodically switching spinning mode leading to beating of the acoustic signals amplitude is observed. The joint PDFs show a very repetitive but slightly asymmetric pattern.
- Though the study features a nominally symmetric setup, the anti-nodal line location of the standing component follows a clear, repeatable pattern path. The system clearly exhibits two preferred nodal line positions. This indicates that even nominally symmetric combustor can exhibit small asymmetries that

do alter and can dominate the response of the system. The source of the asymmetry remains unknown.

- At the largest equivalence ratio (and amplitude, far from the bifurcation) only spinning modes (switching for 4 kW) were observed while low amplitude instabilities close to the bifurcation tend to exhibit dynamics around a standing mode.
- For 6 kW case, a small increase in equivalence ratio resulted in the 1A2L mode hopping to the slightly higher frequency 1A3L mode. This was accompanied by more than a doubling of the acoustic velocity amplitude which modified the mean flame shape by making it more compact. A possible explanation is that this length change has the effect of inducing a change in the FTF delay and the linear stability of the system to favour the 3L longitudinal component of the mode.

This work provides a valuable experimental data set with several interesting phenomena that are related to modal dynamics in annular combustors under transient operation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Calculation of the slow-flow variables

This section aims to shed light onto the post processing routine to calculate the slow flow variables.

We take the three azimuthally distributed pressure signals $p_{0,1}$, $p_{1,1}$ and $p_{2,1}$ as a starting point and use a FFT to determine the dominant mode. This is without exception the mode with azimuthal mode order $n = 1$ in the present work. Each pressure time series is then bandpass-filtered with a bandpass width of $\Delta f = 100$ Hz around the corresponding peak frequency f to remove noise components.

The spatial pressure field $p(\Theta, t)$ is 2π -periodic because of the annular shape of the chamber. It can therefore be written as a Fourier series for the azimuthal coordinate Θ , and this series is truncated to the 1st order terms because the filtering allowed us

to get rid of the higher order components:

$$p(\Theta, t) = \xi_1(t) \cos(\Theta) + \xi_2(t) \sin(\Theta). \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The projected signals ξ_1 and ξ_2 are obtained from the filtered microphone timetraces by inverting the system

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_{0,1} \\ p_{1,1} \\ p_{2,1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\Theta_0) & \sin(\Theta_0) \\ \cos(\Theta_1) & \sin(\Theta_1) \\ \cos(\Theta_2) & \sin(\Theta_2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1 \\ \xi_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where Θ describes the azimuthal position of the microphones. In the present study $\Theta_0 = 0$, $\Theta_1 = 2\pi/3$ and $\Theta_2 = 4\pi/3$. This system is overdetermined and is inverted in a least square sense. The corresponding complex analytic signals of ξ_1 and ξ_2 are

$$\xi_{a,1}(t) = \xi_1(t) + j\mathcal{H}(\xi_1(t)) \quad \xi_{a,2}(t) = \xi_2(t) + j\mathcal{H}(\xi_2(t)) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where \mathcal{H} is the Hilbert transform and j the second quaternion imaginary unit. The quaternion analytic signal of $\xi(t)$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_a(t) &= \xi_{a,1} + i\xi_{a,2} \\ &= \xi_1 + i\xi_2 + j\mathcal{H}(\xi_1(t)) + k\mathcal{H}(\xi_2(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

with i, j, k as the quaternion imaginary units. From this point, the slow-flow variables A, χ, θ, φ are extracted from ξ_a with the method presented in the appendix of [30].

Supplementary material

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:[10.1016/j.combustflame.2020.10.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2020.10.013).

References

- [1] M.R. Bothien, A. Ciani, J.P. Wood, G. Fruechtel, Toward decarbonized power generation with gas turbines by using sequential combustion for burning hydrogen, *J. Eng. Gas Turb. Power* 141 (2019) 121013.
- [2] G. Glenk, S. Reichelstein, Economics of converting renewable power to hydrogen, *Nat. Energy* 4 (2019) 216–222.
- [3] T. Lieuwen, V. Yang, Combustion Instabilities In Gas Turbine Engines: Operational Experience, Fundamental Mechanisms, and Modeling, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Inc., 2005.
- [4] T. Poinsot, Prediction and control of combustion instabilities in real engines, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 36 (2017) 1–28.
- [5] W. Krebs, P. Flohr, B. Prade, S. Hoffmann, Thermoacoustic stability chart for high intensity gas turbine combustion systems, *Combust. Sci. Tech.* 174 (2002) 99–128.
- [6] J.R. Seume, N. Vortmeyer, W. Krause, J. Hermann, C.-C. Hantschk, P. Zangl, S. Gleis, D. Vortmeyer, A. Orthmann, Application of active combustion instability control to a heavy duty gas turbine, *J. Eng. Gas Turb. Power* 120 (1998) 721–726.
- [7] N. Noiray, B. Schuermans, On the dynamic nature of azimuthal thermoacoustic modes in annular gas turbine combustion chambers, *Proc. R. Soc. A-Math. Phys.* 469 (2013) 20120535.
- [8] N.A. Worth, J.R. Dawson, Modal dynamics of self-excited azimuthal instabilities in an annular combustion chamber, *Combust. Flame* 160 (2013) 2476–2489.
- [9] N.A. Worth, J.R. Dawson, Self-excited circumferential instabilities in a model annular gas turbine combustor: Global flame dynamics, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 34 (2013) 3127–3134.
- [10] J.-F. Bourgoign, D. Durox, J.P. Moeck, T. Schuller, S. Candel, Self-sustained instabilities in an annular combustor coupled by azimuthal and longitudinal acoustic modes, *ASME Turbo Expo* (2013) Paper No: GT2013-95010.
- [11] P. Wolf, G. Staffelbach, L.Y. Gicquel, J.-D. Müller, T. Poinsot, Acoustic and large eddy simulation studies of azimuthal modes in annular combustion chambers, *Combust. Flame* 159 (2012) 3398–3413.
- [12] J.-F. Bourgoign, D. Durox, J.P. Moeck, T. Schuller, S. Candel, Characterization and modeling of a spinning thermoacoustic instability in an annular combustor equipped with multiple matrix injectors, *J. Eng. Gas Turb. Power* 137 (2014) 021503.
- [13] A. Faure-Beaulieu, T. Indlekofer, J.R. Dawson, N. Noiray, Experiments and low-order modelling of intermittent transitions between clockwise and anticlockwise spinning thermoacoustic modes in annular combustors, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* (2020), doi:[10.1016/j.proci.2020.05.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2020.05.008).
- [14] M. Bauerheim, M. Cazalens, T. Poinsot, A theoretical study of mean azimuthal flow and asymmetry effects on thermo-acoustic modes in annular combustors, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 35 (2015) 3219–3227.
- [15] A. Morgans, S. Stow, Model-based control of combustion instabilities in annular combustors, *Combust. Flame* 150 (2007) 380–399.
- [16] M. Bauerheim, P. Salas, F. Nicoud, T. Poinsot, Symmetry breaking of azimuthal thermo-acoustic modes in annular cavities: a theoretical study, *J. Fluid Mech.* 760 (2014) 431–465.
- [17] P. Berenbrink, S. Hoffmann, Suppression of dynamic combustion instabilities by passive and active means, *ASME Turbo Expo* (2000) Paper No: 2000-GT-0079.
- [18] N. Noiray, M. Bothien, B. Schuermans, Investigation of azimuthal staging concepts in annular gas turbines, *Combust. Theor. Model.* 15 (2011) 585–606.
- [19] J.P. Moeck, M. Paul, C.O. Paschereit, Thermoacoustic instabilities in an annular Rijke tube, *ASME Turbo Expo* (2010) Paper No: GT2010-23577.
- [20] J.R. Dawson, N.A. Worth, The effect of baffles on self-excited azimuthal modes in an annular combustor, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 35 (2015) 3283–3290.
- [21] G. Ghirardo, M.P. Juniper, J.P. Moeck, Weakly nonlinear analysis of thermoacoustic instabilities in annular combustors, *J. Fluid Mech.* 805 (2016) 52–87.
- [22] T.C. Lieuwen, Experimental investigation of limit-cycle oscillations in an unstable gas turbine combustor, *J. Propul. Power.* 18 (2002) 61–67.
- [23] P. Knoop, F. Culick, E. Zukoski, Extension of the stability of motions in a combustion chamber by nonlinear active control based on hysteresis, *Combust. Sci. Tech.* 123 (1997) 363–376.
- [24] S. Manikandan, R. Sujith, Rate dependent transition to thermoacoustic instability via intermittency in a turbulent afterburner, *Exp. Therm. Fluid Sci.* 114 (2020) 110046.
- [25] G. Bonciolini, N. Noiray, Bifurcation dodge: avoidance of a thermoacoustic instability under transient operation, *Nonlinear Dyn.* 96 (2019) 703–716.
- [26] G. Bonciolini, D. Ebi, U. Doll, M. Weilenmann, N. Noiray, Effect of wall thermal inertia upon transient thermoacoustic dynamics of a swirl-stabilized flame, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 37 (2019) 5351–5358.
- [27] W. Culler, X. Chen, J. Samarasinghe, S. Peluso, D. Santavica, J. O'Connor, The effect of variable fuel staging transients on self-excited instabilities in a multiple-nozzle combustor, *Combust. Flame* 194 (2018) 472–484.
- [28] K. Prieur, D. Durox, T. Schuller, S. Candel, A hysteresis phenomenon leading to spinning or standing azimuthal instabilities in an annular combustor, *Combust. Flame* 175 (2017) 283–291.
- [29] M. Mazur, H.T. Nygård, J.R. Dawson, N.A. Worth, Characteristics of self-excited spinning azimuthal modes in an annular combustor with turbulent premixed bluff-body flames, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 37 (2019) 5129–5136.
- [30] G. Ghirardo, M.R. Bothien, Quaternion structure of azimuthal instabilities, *Phys. Rev. Fluids* 3 (2018) 113202.
- [31] JulHoltz, Julia package for handling various wave equations and (non-linear) eigenvalue problems. <https://github.com/JulHoltzDevelopers/WavesAndEigenvalues.jl>.
- [32] D. Laera, T. Schuller, K. Prieur, D. Durox, S.M. Camporeale, S. Candel, Flame describing function analysis of spinning and standing modes in an annular combustor and comparison with experiments, *Combust. Flame* 184 (2017) 136–152.
- [33] G. Bonciolini, D. Ebi, E. Boujo, N. Noiray, Experiments and modelling of rate-dependent transition delay in a stochastic subcritical bifurcation, *R. Soc. Open Sci.* 5 (2018) 172078.
- [34] E.A. Gopalakrishnan, R.I. Sujith, Effect of external noise on the hysteresis characteristics of a thermoacoustic system, *J. Fluid Mech.* 776 (2015) 334–353.
- [35] J.R. Dawson, N.A. Worth, Flame dynamics and unsteady heat release rate of self-excited azimuthal modes in an annular combustor, *Combust. Flame* 161 (2014) 2565–2578.